

THE THINKING DEVELOPMENT OF PHYSICAL CULTURE AND SPORT WITH ELEMENTS OF WEIGHTLIFTING DURING SELECTIVE COURSE LESSON

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Abstract: *The article describes the methods of theoretical research that allow creating the concept of forming a student's thinking by means of physical culture with elements of weightlifting, as well as empirical methods of studying.*

Keywords: *thinking, development, physical culture, student, elements of weightlifting, educational organization of higher education, sports, physical culture, exercises.*

Modern psychological science, intensively developing, interacts with other sciences, and, consequently, new directions and problems appear, and therefore new branches appear. Currently, researchers and scientists often resort to studying the specifics of the psychological qualities of representatives of any professions. Physical culture and sports, being a significant social phenomenon, are also subjected to psychological analysis of the personal qualities of students.

There are studies of an ascertaining nature that have revealed specific psychological features of the activity and personality of students in different sports. Some researchers study the influence of psychological qualities on achievements in competitions and the success of performances. Scientists in their research considered psychological and intellectual qualities. Foreign scientist J. Afremov in his scientific work provides an analysis of the content of the athlete's thoughts.

Within the framework of the main professional educational program, there is a variable part, which includes an elective course in physical culture with elements of weightlifting, the scope of which includes author's classes that contribute to the development of students' thinking. Let's consider the effectiveness of the development of students' thinking with the help of the author's elective course with elements of weightlifting.

To work with students in the framework of an elective course, or in preparation for competitions, knowledge of psychological qualities and personality traits is necessary. Pedagogical aspects of working with students involve consideration of the student's personality for at least 4-6 years, that is, on the path of formation - training in an educational organization of higher education. The teacher should understand due to what processes and what features are formed in students when performing assigned tasks in weightlifting. And also clearly realize that thinking unfolds in space,

the dynamics of the development of thinking in different age periods are different and how the transfer of thinking into social, professional or educational activities is carried out.

The possibilities of developing the thinking of students in professional sports are much higher than those of students who do not play sports. For example, orienteering students have formed thinking - this is a complex and multi-valued phenomenon, since when solving spatial problems, searching for objects on the ground, they represent a model of space from a map with the translation of symbols into imaginary terrain objects based on subjective experience. In rhythmic gymnastics, due to the limitation of the place of performance, the athlete is forced to solve spatial problems, since the movement of the body must be harmoniously coordinated with the movement of objects. Gymnasts' thinking is trained and is subject-oriented, constructive. Therefore, some trainers introduce topological approach training in training, thereby forming topological thinking. Modern weightlifting solves the same problems as gymnastics, since in these sports there is a limitation of the place of performance. Athletes need to solve problems with the movement of objects, while considering the relationship between weightlifting and barbell, in this case, subject-based thinking, constructing.

Power sports involve concentration of attention, intellectual and volitional tension, which contributes to the formation and development of thinking in accordance with tactical and technical actions.

Thinking is a generalized or internally mediated form of human informational interaction with the surrounding reality, which establishes a connection and relationships between any objects of cognition. Sports thinking is thinking realized in a certain sports activity.

Individual peculiarities of thinking are evaluated by identifying the qualities of the student. After analyzing the scientific literature, the following qualities of thinking can be distinguished: independence, depth, breadth, flexibility, criticality, speed. An individual combination of such qualities characterizes the style of intellectual activity of the student. Studies of the life of athletes convincingly show that strenuous physical labor contributes to the improvement of intellectual activity, which forms and develops intellectual abilities necessary in sports and for life in society. After analyzing the biographies of outstanding athletes, it was revealed that these people are very versatile personalities who have achieved high results outside of sports. In modern society, there is an illusion that many athletes do not show high intellectual abilities, let's consider the reasons for the appearance of such an opinion.

Reason 1. Not all athletes realize the existing development potential.

Reason 2. Incredible efforts and overstrain have a negative impact on the functioning of the nervous system.

Thought processes are the basis of tactical actions, and proceed according to the principle of the acceptor of action, which involves activity in finding a solution to the

task with the help of associative connections that appear from the acquired experience and available information. To improve the speed of solving tactical tasks, it is necessary to improve the ability of heuristic automated search. Since the complexity of making the right decision is directly related to a large variety of intersubject connections and connections between phenomena, as well as in a limited amount of time allotted for decision-making.

Another difficulty in making a decision is related to the choice between desire and fear of failure. When performing strength exercises, visual analyzers record a lot of nano-details: ease when lifting the barbell, calculation of approaches, weight gain options, well-being. The left hemisphere of the brain for analytical processing of information takes a minute to make an adequate conclusion. The right hemisphere captures the whole picture, comparing it with the pictures imprinted in memory, and gives a signal for making the right decision. A person is not aware of all the information processed by the brain, the speed of unconscious operations is higher than the speed of analytical thinking with conscious information processing. The athlete gets the impression that the idea was "prompted" by intuition, although such an assumption is a delusion, since a trained brain instantly generates the right decisions.

Domestic psychologist

S.L. Rubinstein means that automatism and skills are turning off from the field of consciousness of individual components of actions that are the result of learning, repetition, training, exercises; accumulation of professional experience necessary for successful activity, images, knowledge, techniques of operating with them, in other words, the development of subconsciousness, intuition. Heavy athletics performs complex coordination movements, high achievements in this sport are possible only with the improvement of speed-strength and coordination qualities, the development potential of which depends on the development of thinking.

Conclusion: During the research and interviews with students, it was revealed that the predominant value is physical activity in classes on an elective course with elements of weightlifting. Since it stimulates many organs and tissues of the body, including nerve cells of the brain, accelerates the development and branching of neural processes.

When performing strength exercises, blood circulation and respiration increase, which supply the brain with nutrients and oxygen, vital for productive work. The enhanced development of neural networks extends to other areas of the brain, such as thinking and memory, which are the main ones in learning. During the performance of strength exercises, branches of nerve cells are intensively formed and grow, causing all intellectual processes. Brain development occurs due to high-quality and regular physical activity. As a result of an experimental study of students attending elective classes with elements of weightlifting, it can be concluded that students think more

quickly, clearly and qualitatively, they do not have fatigue, which contributes to greater endurance of intellectual abilities.

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